

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE USE OF SOCIAL NETWORKS IN ADMINISTRATION CAREER STUDENTS

Gilberto Mejía Salazar

Autonomous University of Nayarit

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Abstract

The objective of the following investigation is to know the frequency of use that the student gives to social networks from the educational perspective, as well as to deliberate the usefulness of these technological tools. A quantitative approach was used, therefore, a survey with closed questions was applied for data collection. For data processing, frequencies were used to analyze the collected data. Obviously, social networks help to obtain and exchange information about tasks, jobs, research projects, and positively influence the student's academic training. Being a widely used and practical medium in daily activities, proper use allows solving problems in the classroom. The frequency of use of social networks by students is 52.6%, referring to what they do every day, it is established that the use of social networks gives the opportunity to be connected with the same classmates and teachers, developing activities and tasks inside and outside the school or campus, and at the same time promoting collective and organized work. In addition, the student declares to be connected to the internet and social networks for two to three hours (37.2%).

Keywords: Communication, education, teaching by computer, internet, social network.

Introduction

Social networks in the field of education have gained favoritism for the use of these same, establishing and granting an endless number of technological tools available to all, that is, social, educational and work environments have driven this type of tools to be part of strategies, proposals and initiatives that are focused on general improvement. In this way, knowing these tools constitutes an advance within the institutions, achieving the support they give to students and teachers, carrying out a continuous activity in the pedagogical functions.

Likewise, the benefits are of great magnitude consolidating the important aspects for the academic development of the student, social networks arise not only to make playful use of them, but also provide opportunities for the performance and understanding of the subjects, give support for research, tasks, teamwork, consultation of information and above all maintain communication with teachers and students, highlighting that the main objective of this research is based on knowing the frequency of use and the application of social networks, in addition, to investigate the usefulness it gives to the same people.

Finally, the research provides results on the use and frequencies of these technological tools, which at the same time works with the proposed objective, taking these results to deliberate the constancy itself. We live in a digital environment where technology is able to attract the attention of users. Thus, the so-called social networks are an instrument for teaching and learning, determining models in education.

Social media in education

The challenges of social networks are focused on offering spaces where continuous and self-taught learning is favored, and in this way to be able to adapt it to an effective learning plan or scheme. For Islas and Caranza [5] "they define that social networks constitute one of the most representative tools of web 2.0, since

their roots and fascination in students are a huge didactic possibility".

From the above, it is defined that social networks serve as support in the educational training of the student, giving a range of possibilities to develop the different activities of the school type, providing their own benefits that only in social networks can be found, complementing in direct strategies towards the institutions that make use of these same.

However, social networks offer environments for the creation of work groups where people such as students and teachers can coincide more effectively, creating networks of creative and group collaboration, opting for teamwork, problem solving and project realization.

Therefore, Ruiz [9], affirms that, "social networks are an educational resource, where they create spaces for the formation of closed groups, forming a true virtual collective learning community". In the same way, "they have influenced the way in which citizens are informed about current affairs, displacing traditional media"[10].

The use of social networks in the classroom

The use of social networks has the benefits that they are interactive tools, favoring the development of digital skills, encouraging the search for information and in the same way exchanging information to offer alternatives for school feedback from the virtual approach. Likewise, social networks allow students to develop and exploit their skills, through cognitive processes, which thanks to the transformation and manipulation of information, provide the necessary knowledge to explore in a computer network, which can be available to everyone.

In this way, The World Educational Network (REDEM) [8], argues "that cognitive processes evolve at a high level for the development of these same capacities, such as: reasoning, critical capacity, synthesis and analysis and decision making".

Using social networks in educational centers as pedagogical tools, is gaining strength, because the new generations of students, integrate this type of technologies, adopt digital applications in their living environments, constituting an advance in education, making it clear that anywhere they can access a large amount of information simultaneously.

At the same time, teachers are immersed in challenges where they must embark on a path of technological literacy, for the design of strategies that take the student orientation on the right path [4]. Thus, networks allow machine learning and promote the constant knowledge of students, having different ways of interacting in social and academic tones, for Molina [7], social networks encourage individuals to develop their own knowledge. Therefore, social networks have now

become a very necessary tool and in many cases essential in our daily lives both in the workplace and academically [6].

Benefits of social networks

Social networks have been implemented at different educational levels from three perspectives: as a complement to face-to-face courses, as the main environment for teaching and as a communication forum for networked exchanges of information and knowledge [7]. In this way, it is understood that technologies are in favor of education, showing themselves to be great allies in the activities of knowledge exchange.

With all the above, the type of reinforcement provided by social networks in school environments is made known, defining certain characteristics that manage to combine diverse activities with students, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Academic activities with the use of social networks

Obviously, social networks help to obtain and exchange information about tasks, jobs, research projects, and positively influence the student's academic training. Thus, they are a widely used and practical means in daily activities; the proper use allows solving problems within the classroom. Certainly, through social networks we can have more knowledge and information about what happens around the world, in addition, we can know different things within school environments through social networks. According to social networks are tools that teach new ways of working and teaching, from the educational perspective strategies focused on virtual environments are carried out, capturing the attention of students in general, likewise, Buxarras [2], affirms that social networks offer a whole world of information and possibilities of interconnectivity.

Based on teaching and learning, facilitating better performance within schools, giving opportunity to the

exchange of information between institutions, facilitating a better understanding of knowledge, so it turns out that social networks are important in the integration of present educational models.

It is worth mentioning that virtual environments are not socially or culturally neutral, but carry socio-cultural implications and interpretations that guide and organize social practice [3].

However, the main activity of social networks is marked by communication, in this way, Barrón-Colin and Mejía-Alvarado [1], define that communication exists a transmitter and a receiver, achieving a dynamic and instantaneous process, where users of social networks can be in communication simultaneously.

Main objective

The objective of the research is to know the frequency of use that the student gives to social networks from the educational perspective, as well as to deliberate the usefulness of these technological tools during

the development of activities in the 2020-2021 school year.

Research question

With the above defined, the following research question is reached, do social networks positively influence the academic training of students?

Methodology

To develop the following research, a quantitative approach was used; therefore, for the collection of the data a survey with closed questions was applied. The area of study was carried out in the Academic Unit of Accounting and Administration belonging to the Autonomous University of Nayarit. For data processing, frequencies were used to analyze the collected data.

Sample

To obtain the study sample, the technique of non-probabilistic sampling for convenience was applied; this type of sampling allows the researcher to convincingly select the subjects to study from the same convenience of the researcher [11]. Thus establishing a sample of 78 students to investigate.

Results

Fig. 2. Which social networks do you connect to?

Likewise, it was asked what use it gives to social networks, 36.7% send and receive messages, 7.5% multimedia exchange, 31.3% send assignments and works, 0.7% participate in debates, 10.9% exchange information and knowledge, 12.9% use them for fun and leisure.

What kind of technological tools does the school have? 37% answered that the internet, 33.6% educational platforms, 9.6% specific software, 19.2% basic elements of the computer, and only 0.7% do not know.

Finally, they asked what the means of communication with your teacher is, 1.7% answered that blogs, 13.2% email, 5.8% chats, 38% through platforms, 7.4% Facebook, 33.1% Whatsapp, and 0.8% use another means of communication with the teacher.

Discussion

Of the results obtained, it is necessary that of the total of the participants 59% have computer equipment of which 41% do not have a computer, making it im-

possible to have a relationship with technology, denying the collective work that this type of device can offer. That is why, the places where the student makes use of the internet and in the same way the use of social networks are presented, it is observed that 73.1% have access from home, defining the highest item and it is known that most students have their own network, making efficient the tools and social networks that are very useful.

Likewise, 2.6% make use of the internet from school, providing this service within the reach of students and teachers, providing the necessary tools within the campus to be able to carry out a teaching based on technologies, 6.4% do it at work, 12.8% in the Internet café, and only 5.1% do not have access to the internet, it is understood that within some communities it can be complicated to have this type of technology, Making it impossible to have an online education, this is set to geographical regions that are difficult to access or simply not have the services available today.

The results show that of the total number of students surveyed, 46 are female and 32 are male, of which 59% of students have a computer and 41% do not have a computer. In the same way, they asked where they have access to the internet, 73.1% have access at home, 2.6% at school, 6.4% at work, 12.8% in the Internet café and only 5.1% do not have access to the internet.

What is the frequency of use of social networks by students, 52.6% use social networks every day, 35.9% some days, 10.3% once a week and 1.3% do not use social networks. Within this context, 35.9% connect to social networks less than an hour, 37.2% two to three hours, 15.4% four to five hours, 6.4% six to seven hours, and 5.1% more than nine hours. Of the above, it was asked which social networks do you connect to? 38.7% connect to Facebook, 4.2% Snapchat, 1.2% Twitter, 18.5% Messenger, 20.8% YouTube, 0.6% Pinterest, 8.3% Instagram, 7.1% connect to another social network and only 0.6% do not connect, as seen in figure 2.

Thus, the frequency of use of social networks by students is 52.6% referring that they do it every day, 35.9% some days, 10.3% once a week and 1.3% do not use social networks, it is therefore established that the use of social networks gives the opportunity to be connected with the same classmates and teachers, developing activities and tasks inside and outside the school or campus, and at the same time promoting collective and organized work, having social and playful interaction for the benefit of people, making it clear that the use of social networks is attractive for students in general. In addition, the student declares to be connected to the internet and social networks for two to three hours (37.2%).

Within this context, it is referenced that the social networks most used and frequented by students is the aforementioned social network Facebook (38.7%), Messenger 18.5%, and YouTube (20.8%), these networks being the preferred. Therefore, it follows that 36.7% send and receive messages, 31.3% send assignments and works, reiterating that social networks focused on the educational field are of great help in the management and organization of students' homework, providing their own benefits, and only 12.9% use them for fun and leisure.

In this way, 38% of the students stay in communication through platforms, and 33.1% do it through Whatsapp, which results in frequent favorable and beneficial management for the student community, deliberating that social networks are tools of great help within the environment of the institution.

Conclusion

It should be concluded that the research yields favorable results, projecting the main objective, which is to know the frequency of use and their usefulness, which confirms the question posed, do social networks have a positive influence on the academic training of students? in this sense it is expressed that social networks can exchange information with peers, influencing knowledge. In the same way, between groups it is possible to complete the most appropriate information and to be able to share it.

It should be noted that it is important to have access to this type of technology because it is a way of communicating with teachers, and it is easier for students to use. As is known, the use and knowledge of social networks helps to improve academic training, facilitating knowledge and information about culture, technology, history, art, etc.

However, thanks to social networks you can search and consult information for student tasks, they facilitate research on various topics, the truth is that, if

social networks are applied correctly, you can learn beneficial things. Finally, it is considered that social networks are fundamental tools today that facilitate school work: research, feedback, courses, among others.

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